

Ecstasy of learning, teaching and research experience in a university environment

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Introduction

I am highly beholden to the Indian Chemical Society, for bestowing upon me the prestigious Platinum Jubilee Award in recognition of my humble life-long devotion to Inorganic and Metallo-organic Chemistry along with four other distinguished colleagues in different fields. Frankly, the credit for this unsolicited honour is entirely due to my students, coworkers and colleagues for their whole-hearted collaboration and original contributions, coupled with some recognition which they have indirectly brought to their humble teacher by their brilliant accomplishments and continued achievements in India as well as abroad (*cf.* the last portion of this presentation).

In order to elucidate the development of feelings of 'Ecstasy for learning, teaching and research experience', a very brief personal account appears to be essential. Having given up my ambition of joining the Civil Services due to patriotic feelings generated by an active participation in the Quit India Movement in 1942, it was my earnest desire to get into the teaching profession at any level. It was finally a stroke of sheer luck that on the basis of my academic career, I was appointed a lecturer in 1944 in my own alma-mater (Allahabad University) even against the wishes of the then Head of the Department, who assigned me with immediate effect teaching work at all levels including M.Sc. (Final) in inorganic chemistry, although I had studied only Physical Chemistry at that level. Under the circumstances, I had to work extremely hard to master the rudiments of important topics in inorganic chemistry. Fortunately, my basic knowledge in physical chemistry was very helpful in explaining the mechanism of inorganic reactions and the structural aspects of inorganic compounds, which was highly appreciated by the brilliant students of the then flourishing Allahabad University. The depth of interest which I began to develop towards inorganic chemistry during these penetrating studies seeded in me a desire to carry out research work in the same area of chemistry. It may not be out of place to recall that although a considerable amount of research work had been carried out in our country including Allahabad University in the branches of physical and or-

ganic chemistry, yet there was hardly any research activity in inorganic chemistry except under the leadership of Acharya P. C. Ray and later, under his able disciple, Prof. Priyadarajan Ray at Kolkata.

Sensing my keenness for research in inorganic chemistry, my teachers of physical chemistry at Allahabad University were very kind to suggest some research problems but somehow those could not fascinate me sufficiently. I approached even Prof. P. Ray in Kolkata requesting him to take me as his research student, emphasizing that I was willing to resign my post of lecturer at Allahabad University. However, to my misfortune, he had no funds/scholarship available. Being unable to initiate any meaningful and sustained research work, my attention was focussed mainly on improving the quality of teaching, in which I was amply rewarded by the unique experience of identifying my early research problems from the searching/penetrating questions of my students; this has ever since heightened my eagerness to continue in the university environment where such free interactions are more easily possible and feasible.

Search for research problem(s) (from students)

The first such experience was the B.Sc. part I students' failure to verify the Blue Mantle test from a mixture of tin salt, zinc and sulfuric acid, as taught by me on the basis of a text book of analytical chemistry being published by my colleagues. A careful survey of the original literature, however, revealed that the actual test required hydrochloric in place of sulfuric acid (as had been wrongly instructed by me). The mistake was, therefore, easily rectified during the next class with my apologies to the students. However, as the test had been ascribed to the burning of tin hydride formed by the reduction of tin salt with nascent hydrogen produced in the system by the reaction of zinc with the acid, curiosity was aroused in me from such different behavior of the system with the change of the acid reagent employed and this gave me my first research problem. I did publish two papers (ascribing the phenomenon to Chemiluminescence) in addition to a letter to *Nature*¹, on the basis of the investigations which I carried out to understand the difference.

My next research problem came from the M.Sc. students whom I was teaching about the applications of adsorption indicators in argentometric titrations. In this connection, I gave them a list of indicators from an extensive review article, published by Fajans, the discoverer of Adsorption Indicators, only a few months earlier. On learning that most of these indicators were phthalein dyes (derived from the dibasic phthalic acid), one of the two students who has now retired after serving as a distinguished professor of Inorganic Chemistry at B.I.T.S., Pilani, asked me whether similar dyes derived from dibasic acids (about which they had been taught in the M.Sc. Previous by their teacher of organic chemistry Dr. S. Dutta who had carried out considerable research work in these directions) other than phthalic acid could also serve the purpose. I admitted to my students that I did not know the answer and would inform them about the same afterwards. On a careful survey of the literature, I found that dyes from other dibasic acids had not been tried for their applicability as indicators. This naturally gave me another research problem on which I published more than a dozen independent research papers not only on the use of new (even reversible) indicators, in prestigious journals like *Journal of Indian Chemical Society* and *Analytica Chimica Acta*, but also on a novel explanation of their applicability on 'surface compound formation'. The work was extensively reviewed with favourable comments in *Zeitschrift für Analytische Chemie* and I was invited to present a lecture on the topic at the meeting of the Gesellschaft Deutscher Chemiker held at Cologne in 1951. Many years later, I suggested extension of the investigations to a keen aspirant teacher of a degree college, the examiner of whose Ph.D. thesis being the Editor of *Talanta* invited me to write a review article² on the 'Applications and Theory of Adsorption Indicators'.

Another research problem, which also was included in my D.Phil. Thesis (1948) at Allahabad University, arose from a searching question by an undergraduate student about the actual mechanism of softening of water by Calgon (known erroneously at that time as 'sodium hexametaphosphate'). Again a survey of the literature revealed no enlightenment in this direction. This led me to the synthesis of polymeric complexes polymetaphosphates of sodium with a large number of other metals, e.g., Ca, Sr, Ba, Pb, Zn, Cd, Ln, Fe, etc. A research fellow at Gorakhpur and two other colleagues later at Rajasthan University obtained their doctorate degrees on their lithium and potassium analogs. The results were presented by me in a number of international conferences on 'Macromolecular Chemistry'. The work was so highly appreciated that I received an unsolicited invitation for a Plenary Lecture³ on the topic at 'The II Interna-

tional Conference on Inorganic Phosphorus Compounds' at Prague in 1974, and later at Kyoto in 1987.

Research in the field of alkoxides, carboxylates, β -diketonates and other metallo-organic derivatives

The next stage of my research began with my joining the research school of Prof. W. Wardlaw at Birkbeck College, London, as a British Council Scholar. During the period (1950-52), I was deeply impressed by the originality and extraordinary brilliance of Dr. D. C. Bradley (awarded the highest honour of the Royal Medal in U.K. in 1998) and Dr. D. H. R. Barton (later Nobel Laureate) who were working in the same rickety building on the 3rd and 4th floors of laboratory, the basement and the first two floors of which were being used by the famous X-ray crystallographer, Prof. J. D. Bernal for residence-cum-laboratory; this was a makeshift arrangement due to the heavy damage suffered by the buildings of Birbeck College in the east end of London during the War.

Immediately before my joining the group, Dr. Bradley had been awarded the Ph.D. degree of London University on his exciting work dealing with different alkoxides of zirconium. On pondering over the most exciting observation in Bradley's thesis, that $Zr(OBu^t)_4$ could be distilled as a monomeric colourless fluid liquid at $\sim 50^\circ$ under 1 mm pressure, it occurred to me that its fractional distillation could lead to separation of 100% pure $Zr(OBu^t)_4$, as the 1-2% $Hf(OBu^t)_4$ present in natural zirconium sources could be expected to boil at a considerably higher temperature due to its much larger molecular weight; this pure $Zr(OBu^t)_4$ could be thereafter converted easily into Hf-free ZrO_2 required for nuclear reactors, as the slightest amount of Hf tends to enhance its nuclear cross-section considerably thereby reducing the neutron flux. However, after developing a novel more satisfactory transesterification route for preparing about 25 g of $Zr(OBu^t)_4$, its fractionation tended to show larger hafnium content in the more volatile fraction compared to the starting material. In order to verify such intriguing observations, I requested Prof. Wardlaw to get for me from somewhere a few grams of a pure hafnium compound, but I was surprised that in spite of his best efforts, it took 10-12 weeks for a distinguished inorganic chemist like Prof. Wardlaw to procure 10 g of HfO_2 from the I.C.I. laboratories on loan with a promise to return at least 9 g of the sample after experimentation. I immediately synthesized half a dozen different pure alkoxides of hafnium and was extremely surprised that each of these had a boiling point, 1-2° lower than that of the corresponding Zr analog. The original idea of Zr-Hf separation by this technique was consequently given up, but the reason for the slightly higher volatility of

Hf derivatives compared to their Zr analogs is not as yet fully understood. The difficulties in procuring a few grams of a hafnium compound in London reminded me of a similar experience at Allahabad, where my Department had expressed its financial inability to procure for me a few grams of 'mercurochrome' from the local market to enable me to compare its properties with the corresponding 'argento-chrome', the formation of which type of surface compounds appeared to explain according to me the functioning of some 'adsorption indicators' in argentometric titrations, as mentioned earlier². A poor teacher like me had, therefore, been compelled to squeeze out the money from his own pocket for the purchase of the small amount of mercurochrome required for his experimental purposes.

In a sense, I feel in retrospect lucky for the extremely poor facilities at Birkbeck College, as on returning to India I could somehow manage to initiate work on similar lines with the meagre facilities which I could acquire in the State Universities, which I have chosen to serve throughout my teaching career. The work on metal alkoxides initiated during these two years (1950-52) under such adverse physical facilities had laid a clear base for an extensive and exciting series of investigations on the interesting alkoxide chemistry of almost all the elements in the periodic table (described later in more than 400 original research papers) from our research schools at Lucknow, Gorakhpur and Jaipur.

As I had been able to accumulate more than sufficient work for my doctoral thesis on Group IV metal alkoxides, my formal supervisor Prof. W. Wardlaw had encouraged me to work independently during the last six months of my two years's stay in London along with some teaching assignments. I took advantage of the opportunity in throwing fresh light on the chemistry of aluminium alkoxides. The existing confusion on the extent of oligomerization of the well-known aluminium isopropoxide was clarified⁴ by its 'ageing' property (studied extensively since then for many systems) of changing from a dimeric through trimeric to a comparatively stable tetrameric crystalline form.

In the opinion of alkoxide chemists, the above was an outstanding contribution which not only clarified the existing literature in the field caused by the widely differing observations of a number of earlier well-known chemists, but it laid the foundation of a general behavior of metal alkoxides. In fact, ignoring the advice of sincere friends, I preferred to publish it in the *Journal of Indian Chemical Society*⁴. The impression that publications in our own national journals do not attract adequate attention was nullified by not only repeated enquiries from academic workers, but also from industries like M/s Harshaw Chemical Company of Cleveland (U.S.A). Eight years after the above publi-

cation in 1953, the Harshaw people invited me to resolve a serious problem faced by their small consumers, who found that their aluminium isopropoxide samples when distilled after long storage did not show any tendency of volatilization when heated upto 40–50° above the boiling points at a particular reduced pressure, after which the whole mass of material suddenly poured over. I told them that the reasons were obvious if one read my publication⁴ between the lines, i.e. the aged samples were more polymerized and did not volatilize till the heat of depolymerization was supplied to them and the problem could be easily resolved by maintaining the temperature at near the reported boiling point at the specific pressure till the required heat of depolymerization was imbibed by them to be dissociated into dimeric form, which could be easily detected by the usual slow frothing observed in the distillation process. Raising the temperature slightly and slowly at that stage should result in the desired smooth distillation of the material. On their request, I easily proved my assertion by my actual demonstration to distil one of their aged samples rather fastly, followed by the docile distillation by the slightly modified procedure suggested by me. The company was naturally very happy as it was saved from the bad reputation on the basis of complaints from the larger number of their clients, i.e. small consumers and rewarded me by gifts of special chemicals required by me for our research work back in India for a long time.

The predominant role of steric factors on the properties of metal alkoxides, which had been observed during my Ph.D. work on Group IV alkoxides, was found to be operative in aluminium alkoxides with the difference that the extraordinary stability of the $(\text{RO})_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OR})_2\text{Al}(\text{OR})_2$ bridge, rendered the $(\mu\text{-OR})_2$ groups comparatively much less reactive⁵. During the last week of my stay in London, I came across a long review by the well-known colloid chemists Gray and Alexander⁶, quoting the failures of McBain *et al.* and dozens of other prominent workers in their attempts to prepare aluminium tricarboxylates even by the reactions of aluminium alkoxides with excess of carboxylic acids, leading them to give detailed arguments about their non-existence. Not being at all convinced by the arguments put forth for the non-existence of aluminium tricarboxylates, I dared to repeat the reaction of aluminium isopropoxide with 3 moles of fatty acids in benzene solution under a fractionating column so that the isopropanol produced in the reaction could be continuously fractionated out azeotropically with benzene and could be easily estimated quantitatively. I found that while two isopropoxide groups per aluminium atom could be collected within a few minutes, the replacement of the third group was comparatively much slower and took a few hours for actual completion; the analyses (Al, C and H)

of the final products also tallied exactly with that of aluminium tricarboxylates,

In spite of a clear realization, that the above experimental evidence could be considered valid only if no moisture (from any source, e.g., atmosphere or reagents employed) had been allowed to seep into the system and had to be confirmed by other evidences which I had explicitly in my mind, I took the courage to publish an extremely cautious letter in *Nature*⁷ that the results raised doubts about the vague explanations adduced⁶ for the non-existence of aluminium tri-soaps based on the failures of dozens of colloid chemists to prepare soaps with carboxylate aluminium ratio >2 : 1. I was, therefore, not surprised to receive two letters from well-known authorities in the field like Gray⁶ and Nelson⁸ that the conclusion in my publication was not based on sound and indisputable evidence, but I was particularly peeved to read a comment in one of these letters that this was in keeping with the usual habit of Indian scientists to rush for publication without conclusive evidence. In spite of my hurt feelings, I sent them polite replies that the above could certainly be considered as definitive evidence, only if the whole system was stringently protected from moisture from any source. On my part, I was personally 100% sure, as I had handled dozens of even more hydrolyzable reaction systems with remarkable success. I even clearly indicated the lines of further investigations by which my conclusions could be further confirmed. Admitting my helplessness to carry out any further work due to unavailability of any facilities at Allahabad (where I had returned immediately after I had carried out the work at London and in fact, the C/H analyses were also received by me at Allahabad), I requested them to follow up the work in their laboratories and to confirm or contradict my conclusions.

On my part, I was fully convinced of my conclusions. I was fortunately able to collect further conclusive evidence in that direction with the help of a very able student, K. C. Pande. Fortunately, Nelson and coworkers⁸ also soon after published an article in the *Journal of Chemical Society (London)* in which they began the Abstract of their paper with the unusually worded sentence that "Mehrotra's method for synthesis of aluminium tri-carboxylates is confirmed". They, of course, had the courtesy to apologize to me profusely in a personal letter.

The fact that I was very lucky in eliciting the coopera-

tion of extremely bright and dedicated students in the classroom as well as research coworkers is evinced by the fact that the same K. C. Pande, after submitting his Ph.D. thesis came to me expressing doubts about the trimeric nature of dichlorotitanium bisacetylacetonate, reported⁹ as [Ti(acac)₃]₂TiCl₆ by highly prominent investigators like Rosenheim as well as Dilthey. Although these findings had been quoted even in the then well-known undergraduate Text Books of inorganic chemistry like the one by Partington, yet I agreed with my young friend, and we immediately chalked out a line of investigation by which the above compound was shown⁹ to be a simple monomeric species, [Ti(acac)₂Cl₂], leading to corrections even in undergraduate text-books.

The experiences cited above have been repeated dozens of times during the last four decades and I have been lucky to learn from the remarks of my younger colleagues and students to the mutual benefit of all concerned. With such unbounded joy emanating from the happy student-teacher relationships, I have naturally considered myself very fortunate and never thought of leaving the teaching profession, in spite of many attractive and lucrative offers received during the period from National Laboratories as well as from abroad. My gratification knew no limits when even the undergraduate students of Rajasthan University vehemently protested before the Syndicate meeting which was considering my application for lien in the University for accepting the Chair vacated by the retirement of late Prof. Seshadri at Delhi University in early 1970's. Although I naturally succumbed to the affectionate pressure of the students, yet as luck would have it, I was left with no option about two years later but to accept the difficult office of the Vice-Chancellor of the same university (Delhi). However, before accepting the office, I made it quite clear that as far as time and energy would permit, I would continue to supervise a few Ph.D. students at Jaipur and also induct a new group of research scholars at Delhi, in addition to taking a few undergraduate/postgraduate classes. Although it meant extremely hard work, I continued daily discussions with research students in early morning (5–8 a.m.) sittings so as to be free for the difficult and annoying administrative chores without any distraction from about 9 a.m. I tried to arrange my classes three times a week from 8–9 a.m. as there was very little chance of any student/teacher/non-teaching leaders to disturb the administration so early in the morning. In order to achieve all this, the administrative work was decentralized in such an effective manner that most of the decisions could be taken at a lower level and the administrative work of the University did not suffer.

As I was devoting the whole of the day after 9 a.m. to my primary duty (administration of the University) at that time, I had no prick of conscience, but I did not consider it fair to my office (which is generally considered a round-the-clock job) to have any routine of academic work in the evening. Not being interested in the social engagements, I often found some spare time in the evenings and could utilize it meaningfully in publishing two^{10,11} of the three¹² books on M-O-C derivatives published by the Academic Press with me as one of the authors. These books, particularly the one on Metal Alkoxides have brought us considerable credit, as the painstaking research work of my coworkers on these topics is generally considered to be a major component of the world knowledge existing on the topic. In addition to revealing novel structural features including the role of steric factors and 'ageing' characteristics, detailed studies on alkoxides of almost all the metals and metalloids in the Periodic Table have revealed interesting gradations. Further, metal alkoxides have proved to be unique starting materials for the synthesis of a wide variety of derivatives like aluminium carboxylates and pure non-hydrated lanthanide tris- β -diketonates which in many cases can not be so far synthesized by any other route. Metal alkoxides have also been employed for the synthesis of a wide variety of metallo-organic compounds, such as dialkyl dithiophosphates¹³, alkylene dithiophosphates and other sulfur ligand derivatives¹⁴ at the suggestion of and with active collaboration of a very worthy colleague, late Dr. Ghanshyam Srivastava, who had started his research career with work on alkoxy derivatives of boron at Gorakhpur in 1958 without even a gas supply and Bunsen burners. Studies have also been extended to nitrogen ligand derivatives¹⁵ particularly with Schiff bases by my colleague, Professor J. P. Tandon, later at Jaipur.

Although the above work on metal alkoxides was carried out mainly for the training of younger colleagues in handling difficult materials under the extremely meagre facilities and under the adverse conditions of our laboratories, yet we have been highly gratified to find that metal alkoxides are becoming the most attractive precursors for the preparation of a large variety of ceramic materials¹⁶, which are finding extensive applications in a number of high technology fields during the last few years, as evinced by the large number of queries and also invitations from advanced laboratories/research institutions as well as dozens of International Conferences for lectures/discussions on different facets of alkoxide chemistry.

Chemistry of heterometallic alkoxides

Heterometallic alkoxides now constitute a fastly devel-

oping class of unique heterometallic stable coordination systems, in which alkoxo derivatives of two or more different metals are bonded together generally by alkoxo-¹⁷⁻¹⁹ but sometimes by chloro-^{20,21} or oxo-^{22,23} bridging ligands. Their structural chemistry including nomenclature and technological applications have been developed specially in our laboratories.

Identified initially during 1924-29 by Meerwein and Bersin²⁴ as Alkoxo - Salts, these compounds were named for the first time in 1972 as 'double alkoxides' by Mehrotra and Mehrotra²⁵ in view of their solubility in organic solvents, volatility and the covalent (nonconducting²⁶) characteristics including those of electropositive alkali, alkaline earth and lanthanide metals. Plausible structures, assigned to them, on the basis of their molecular association, alcoholysis reactions with ramified alcohols, and spectroscopic (mainly NMR) properties, have been *without exception* confirmed^{19,23,25} by X-ray crystallography decades later :

After publishing an excellent review³¹ on 'Coordination compounds with tetraisopropoxoaluminate as a bidentate ligand' in the Priyadarajan Memorial Issue of the *Journal of Indian Chemical Society*, Jagvir Singh extended the study of similar derivatives with later 3d-metals, on the basis of which I was invited to present a Special Lecture³² at the International Conference of Coordination Chemistry at

Toulouse in 1980; a portion of these investigations have been published later^{33,34} and also as P. C. Ray Memorial Lecture³⁵. In addition to the above, the recognition of the above work on heterometallic alkoxides of later transition metals is also signified by an immediate invitation to me by Prof. Emele'us, after listening to my lecture on the topic at Cambridge University, to publish a review article³⁶ in the prestigious series being edited by him, in which I renamed them as 'bimetallic alkoxides'.

In spite of the signal success in the synthesis of stable bimetallic alkoxides of various elements in the Periodic Table, I did not have the daring to extend the synthesis to any triheterometallic species and we ascribed the isolation³⁷ of such species for the first time in 1985 in the case of beryllium to the exceptionally small size of the central beryllium metal :

The above was followed in 1988 by the astonishing synthesis of triheterometallic alkoxides of copper³⁸ and tri- as well as tetraheterometallic alkoxides of some later *3d*-metals³⁹ which were published as invited articles in the Eaborn and Vander Kirk special issues of the two journals, in spite of considerable scepticism about the formation of such stable species, which was again apparent by the name 'mixed alkoxides' assigned to them by Chisholm and Rothwell⁴⁰ as late as 1987.

It is gratifying to place on record that the lingering scepticism about the actual identity of triheterometallic alkoxides has been more recently (1996-99) set at rest by a former coworker (S Mathur) in our group who had himself synthesized many such species for his Ph.D. thesis of the University of Rajasthan and thereafter joined Prof. Veith's group in Germany. He resynthesized some of these and was able to elucidate the crystal structure of many triheterometallic alkoxides, the first one⁴¹ of which was the most exciting as it involved the migration of isopropoxometallate groups to render the derivatives more stable :

I have myself been often surprised why I have stuck to synthetic metal alkoxide chemistry with brief forays in the chemistry of dialkyl dithiophosphates¹³ and other sulfur¹⁴ as well as nitrogen¹⁵ ligand derivatives in spite of my keen interest in other aspects of physicochemical investigations. On retrospection, I realize that this has been mainly due to

the periodic revelation of some unexpectedly novel aspect(s) which drew me back to the extremely slow synthetic alkoxide chemistry. A recent incident of this type occurred in 1987, during an invited plenary lecture⁴², on 'Synthesis and Reactions of Metal Alkoxides' at the IVth International Workshop held at Kyoto in July 1987. As soon as I finished my presentation, Dislich of Schott Glasswerke of Germany rushed to the platform and commented that 'Dr. Mehrotra! You have proved everything that I have been conjecturing for the past 16 years'. He further explained that based on the ultra-homogeneity of the final mixed-metal ceramic materials obtained by hydrolysis of mixtures of alkoxides of different metals through the sol-gel-process, he had conjectured in a paper⁴³ published in 1971, that this exceptionally high homogeneity could not be explained merely by the better efficiency of mixing at the molecular level in solution, but it appeared to point to the formation of complex(es) initially in the mixture of many metal alkoxides employed. He was so highly overjoyed by my success in the isolation and characterization of scores of mixed metal alkoxide species that next year in 1988, when he received an invitation for a Gordon Research Conference in U.S.A. on ceramic materials, he replied (endorsing a copy of his letter to me) that he would participate only if Dr. Mehrotra was also invited from India, as "he would explain, 'why homogeneous mixed metal ceramics are formed', whereas I would explain how they are formed". I did enjoy my participation at the above Gordon Conference in April 1988 (as I had done in earlier such conferences on inorganic chemistry) and followed it up by the presentation a week later of a paper entitled 'Polymetallic Alkoxides as Precursors for Ceramics'⁴⁴, at the Material Research Society Symposium (III) on 'Better Ceramics through Chemistry' held at Reno (U.S.A.). Obviously, if the random complexation between different metal alkoxides could give a more homogeneous material, a preformed (generally purified by distillation) polymetallic alkoxide should be much more useful in the direction. The idea was immediately well received and has been since then confirmed in many laboratories around the world.

On my part, I was highly encouraged to pursue our work more enthusiastically in these directions further by the isolation and characterization of mixed-metal alkoxide species containing even more than two (three or four) metals, which I had till then, in general termed as 'double alkoxides'.

Being even more convinced by then of our conclusions, we again changed the name of these novel derivatives as 'heterometal alkoxides'⁴⁵ as the earlier suggested name 'polymetallic alkoxides'⁴⁴ could be confused with the polymeric forms of homo-metal alkoxides. The term has since then come in common usage in a number of review ar-

ticles as well as original papers. The formation of these stable (to heat as evinced by their volatility) heterometallic alkoxides formed by simple alkoxide bridges between different metals has thus added a new dimension to heterometallic coordination chemistry⁴⁶. In fact, in a large number of cases, these heterometallic alkoxides like $[Ln\{\mu\text{-OPr}^i\}_2\text{Al(OPr}^i)_2\}_3]$ have been shown to be more stable (volatilized unchanged at $\sim 180^\circ/1\text{ mm}$) than the analogous homometal derivatives like $[\text{Al}\{\mu\text{-OPr}^i\}_2\text{Al(OPr}^i)_2\}_3]$ which disproportionates into dimeric units, $(\text{Pr}^i\text{O})_2\text{Al}(\mu\text{-OPr}^i)_2\text{Al(OPr}^i)_2$ during distillation at about 100° under 1 mm. The latest success⁴⁷ in this direction has been in the synthesis⁴⁷ of fairly stable heterobimetallic alkoxides of bismuth after a lapse of more than three decades of our first (and only one) publication⁴⁸ on the extraordinary instability of simple alkoxides of bismuth.

An entirely novel route for the synthesis of a large series of heterometallic alkoxides has been described during the last few years by the following type of reactions with various glycols⁴⁹ as well as di-⁵⁰ and tri-ethanolamines⁵¹, as being illustrated by one typical example below :

Insoluble in hydrocarbon solvents

Soluble in hydrocarbon solvents

In addition to their novel and exciting structural aspects, interest in study of heterometal alkoxides has been enhanced by the expectation(s) of the synthesis of 'single source' precursors suited to the composition of the specific targeted material(s). Although significant progress has been achieved^{16,42-45,52-54} in these directions also, yet more sustained efforts are still required to modify the ligands attached

to different metals so that these are able to maintain their stoichiometry during the SG or/and MOCVD processes.

Acknowledgements

In conclusion, I would like to express my deep gratitude to all my innumerable students and about ten dozen research coworkers (of whom only about a dozen could be referred to in this brief article) who have been constantly enlightening me by their searching questions. In addition, I am highly beholden to my senior colleagues like (late) Dr. G. Srivastava, Professor A. K. Rai, Professor V. D. Gupta, Dr. C. K. Oza, Dr. R. Bohra and last but not the least Dr. A. Singh whose day-to-day guidance has been of invaluable help for the sustenance of the research group as a whole. These senior and many other coworkers have by now established independent research schools in this as well as other universities.

In fact, the following laudatory remarks by illustrious Board of Editors of the Special Issue of the *Journal of Organometallic Chemistry* speak volumes about their achievements more than that of mine :

"..... It was readily agreed that it could appropriately appear as a special issue (March 1982) of Mehrotra's contribution to organometallic chemistry and of the high regard in which he is held by chemists around the world.

"We seize the opportunity to add our own tribute to Professor Mehrotra, who has given so much to organometallic chemistry, not only through his own highly productive research, but also through the numerous graduates from his group who have gone on to contribute so effectively to the work of leading organometallic centers in many countries....."

I was even more surprised to receive a letter dated April 14, 1990 from William E. Buhro (Washington University in St. Louis, U.S.A.) conveying the following remarks :

".....your work has been a great inspiration to us. In each of our publications, we try to point to the precedent established in your laboratories. We have noticed that your prior studies and synthetic procedures are not always properly acknowledged. I check for this when I referee manuscripts on alkoxide chemistry, and I insist to the editor that your seminal papers must be recognized.

"I am extremely fortunate that Dr. Subhash C. Goel agreed to come to St. Louis and work with me. Each small accomplishment in my laboratory is due to his hands or to his influence. He is among the 2 or 3 most-skilled bench chemists I have ever known. He is clearly the most productive. Additionally, many of our present projects, may be di-

rectly traced to his original ideas, rather to mine. He knows many techniques that I was ever taught, and has put them into widespread practice among my other coworkers. I am sure I shall never find as valuable a coworker again".

Prologue

In retrospect, I feel that my overall life-long experience is beautifully reflected in the following illuminating words of Nobel Laureate S. Chandrashekar⁵⁵:

"The pursuit of science has often been compared to the scaling of mountains, high and not so high. But who amongst us will hope even in imagination to scale the Everest and reach the summit when the sky is blue and the air is still, and in the stillness of the air survey the entire Himalayan range in the dazzling white of the snow stretching to infinity? None of us can hope for a comparable vision of nature and of the unique universe around us. But there is nothing mean or lowly in standing in the valley below and awaiting the sun to rise over Kinchinjunga".

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